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Рада молодих вчених Інституту соціальної та політичної
психології НАПН України**

**РОЗВИТОК НАУКИ ТА ТЕХНІКИ:
ПРОБЛЕМИ І ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ**

**Збірник тез Всеукраїнської науково-практичної
інтернет-конференції з нагоди відзначення
Дня науки-2020 в Україні**

м. Київ, 21 травня 2020 року

Київ-2020

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Р64 Розвиток науки і техніки: проблеми та перспективи: збірник тез Всеукраїнської науково-практичної інтернет-конференції з нагоди відзначення Дня науки- 2020 в Україні (м. Київ, 21 травня 2020 р.). Київ: ДНДІ МВС України, 2020. 540 с.

У збірнику матеріалів Всеукраїнської науково-практичної інтернет-конференції з нагоди відзначення Дня науки-2020 в Україні більше 150 авторів із різних регіонів України представили широкий спектр результатів наукових досліджень щодо актуальних питань розвитку науки та техніки. Особливу увагу приділили проблемам захисту національної безпеки, адміністративно-правовому регулюванню різних сфер суспільного життя, проблемам психології та педагогіки й науково-технічному забезпеченню правоохоронної діяльності. Матеріали конференції адресовано студентам, аспірантам, докторантам, дослідникам, викладачам вищої школи, практичним працівникам та усім тим, хто цікавиться сучасним станом розвитку науки і техніки в Україні та світі.

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SOME METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF FORMATION OF THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF LAWYER IN MODERN CONDITIONS OF INFORMATION GLOBALIZATION

The fast development of information technologies has led to a global digitalization of society. The consequence of such a phenomenon in the field of legal education is the formation of the environment of developed data processing, modular construction of information systems. As a result, the process of accumulation of knowledge for the formation of professional competencies skills has been gradually changing the form of its implementation. Well-known higher education goals, which are exposed in such elements as *knowledge, understanding*, the forms of their obtaining have been changing.

Higher law education institutions are not main source of education any more. Those basic education goals, the achievement of which is the task of higher education, do not get a correspondent positive reflection in society. A high level of knowledge at the absence of skills of their application is a main factor of professional deformation of a future lawyer.

Thus, at the present stage of the process of improvement of a higher lawyer education, the methodology of teaching legal disciplines, the introduction of innovative teaching methods into the educational process, requires drastic changes. The study of professional disciplines shapes a systematic idea about legal process, legal awareness, provides in-depth training for students in the field of jurisprudence. That is why, in our opinion, the need of paying objective attention to the European integration processes, which have been happening in Ukraine at the present time, is a legal teaching priority.

Besides it, the method of teaching the educational material, taking into account the general European approaches and principles, is very important. Undoubtedly, the use of innovative methods changes a usual process of teaching the material and old-fashioned “traditional” methods are replaced by active innovative learning, in the process of which the rules of interaction of the professor and student are corrected: the student becomes not only an active participant of the educational process, but he/she is forced to think independently and solve certain problems, and the teacher becomes a mentor on the way of improving the personality, the relationship between student and teacher will have a form of an equal partnership.

In order to achieve high efficiency in studying, it is necessary to take into account such principles as systemacity, integrity, a combination of different forms of training a professional lawyer. The specificity of teaching legal disciplines is the need to form not only an understanding of the subject in students, but also to give the opportunity to independently develop practical skills of applying the acquired knowledge. At the same time, considerable attention should be paid to the applied component of the educational process of a lawyer.

As the creative component of education grows significantly, the role of all participants in the educational process intensifies, the creative and exploratory independence of students strengthens, and the implementation of the concept of problem-based and interactive learning becomes especially relevant today. During such studies the student enters into a dialogue with the teacher, performs creative, problematic tasks, answers questions that develop analytical and critical thinking, puts questions to the teacher and other participants, i.e. a creative cooperation of the teacher with students is activated (they solve problems together, model situations, evaluate the actions of classmates and their own behavior).

The specified system is confirmed by the fact that during the period of studying, the students are adapted, get used to the traditional methods of education, which leads to the shortage of the number of their independent scientific researches and influences the knowledge quality in a negative way. It seems like they create “comfort zones”, where they feel safe and it blunts the desire to obtain and acquire knowledge in an active way. This is why a main task of teachers in this context is to produce and implement nowadays techniques and methods of study, their alternative implementation in an educational process which provokes an activation of a creative student’s potential.

Taking into account the inseparable link between theory and practice, the teaching of legal disciplines requires a positive disproportion of doctrinal teaching of the material in relation to the relevant practical processing of theoretical knowledge. At the same time, taking into account the pace of development of society, individualization and specialization of acquired knowledge, the change of forces proportion in the ratio of theoretical and practical should be prioritized towards the latter one. In our opinion, this is due to the fact that the narrow specialization of a lawyer requires not so much the theoretical study of educational material, but a relief improvement of practical skills in the process of obtaining.

At the same time, considering the world trends in the field of education, one can emphasize certain scientific and innovative methods that are widely used in the legal disciplines teaching and help to establish a «reasonable balance» between theoretical and practical training. Among them, the method of problem statement, discussions, group work, the brainstorming method, the critical thinking method, mini-research, business and role-playing games, the blitz polls method, etc. should be especially noted.

The case study method (or method of certain training situation) is widely noticeable among the legal teaching methods in the majority of European countries. Its

specific nature contains in a principal denial of a single correct solution, as a result, the students are constrained to take independent decisions and prove them, they participate, jointly with the teacher, in a direct discussion of business situations or tasks (cases), which are usually prepared in a written form and composed on a real facts basis, where the student take part on-the-scene.

The main achievement of this method is that it promotes the development of the ability to analyze situations, evaluate alternatives, gives solving practical problems skills, which is very relevant for a modern specialist. Case study allows increasing the number of practical classes, gradually reducing the teaching of theoretical material by the teacher in favour of improving practical skills. And the theoretical load reduction is compensated by independent processing of the corresponding material.

An effective legal disciplines teaching method is the method of problem-based statement, when the lecture turns into a dialogue, which allows to make the student interested, to involve him in the learning process. The effectiveness of the method is that some problems can be raised by students themselves, during the practical work on the material thus the teacher seeks «individually colored solution» to the problem from the audience, acting as an examiner. However, it should be noted that the organization of problem-based learning is quite complex, it requires not only significant teacher training, but also a good combination of discipline teaching methods.

Nowadays the innovative process in the field of higher law education is shown in the introduction of such new educational forms as a legal clinic. Its goal is to train legal graduates for their future practical activity. Thus it has been already ascertained that the traditional education, which is based on an explanatory illustrative and reproductive method leads only to a process of transfer of ready, known, «final» knowledge to a student (legal norm commenting, scientific definitions explanation etc.). As a result – passive attitude of the students towards education. The education in a legal clinic is built on new technologies: at each phase of education and work in the clinic, the student not only keeps all the information in his/her head, that he/she traditionally obtain in the lectures, at academic lessons, but also tries to apply it to the realities of legal practice through correspondent educational methods.

Consequently, having examined this problem, one can make a conclusion that the innovative forms of legal disciplines teaching deserve special attention, as they provide the required level of material acquiring in the high education institute, promote a creative activity development and research initiative of students, lay the foundation for further understanding and development of legal knowledge, successful application of acquired knowledge in practice. The introduction of innovative technologies into an educational process helps training highly professional, competitive lawyers, able to solve hard scientific-research, professional and creative tasks.

Наукове видання

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